

BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF STUDIES ON BURNOUT IN MIDWIVES

Muhammet ÇANKAYA

Assoc. Prof., Hitit University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Health Management,
muhammetcankaya@hitit.edu.tr, Çorum/Türkiye, 0000-0003-3498-7328

Abstract

The aim of this study was to conduct a bibliometric analysis of research articles on burnout in midwives in journals published in the "Web of Science" database in 2015-2024. The research articles were analysed using the basic data in Web of Science and VoSviewer software. According to the analyses; the highest number of research articles on the subject was published in 2022 (120); the country with the highest number of research articles was Australia (219); the institution with the highest number of publications was "Monash University" in Australia (39); "Peter Van Bogaert" (15) from the University of Antwerp; "Women And Birth" (38) is the journal with the highest number of publications; "European Union" (12) is the institution that provides the most financial support; "Nursing" (397) is the subject area with the highest number of publications. According to the network map analysis, it was found that the most frequently used keyword was "burnout"; the keywords "job satisfaction", "stress" and "Covid-19" were frequently preferred together; the most cited journal was "Journal of Advanced Nursing"; the most cited author was "Christina Maslach"; Australia ranked first in the co-authorship country analysis and the "Griffith University" institution in Australia ranked first in the co-citation analysis. As a result of the study, it has been observed that the subject is still interesting in the academic field and that financial support can be obtained from many institutions, especially the European Union, for studies on the subject.

Keywords: Bibliometric Analysis, Midwife, Midwifery, Burnout, VoSviewer

EBELERDE TÜKENMİŞLİK KONULU ÇALIŞMALARIN BİBLİYOMETRİK ANALİZİ

Öz

Bu çalışmanın amacı; "Web of Science" veri tabanında 2015-2024 yıllarında yayımlanmış dergilerdeki ebelerde tükenmişlik konulu araştırma makalelerinin bibliyometrik analizini yapmaktır. Çalışmada ele alınan araştırma makaleleri Web of Science'daki temel veriler ve VoSviewer programı kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Yapılan analizlere göre; konu ile ilgili araştırma makalelerinin en fazla 2022 yılında (120 adet) yayımlandığı; en fazla araştırma makalesi yapan ülkenin Avustralya (219 adet) olduğu; en fazla yayın yapan kurumun Avustralya'daki "Monash University" (39 adet) olduğu; en fazla yayın yapan yazarın Antwerp Üniversitesi'nde görev yapan "Peter Van Bogaert" (15 adet) olduğu; en fazla yayın yapan derginin "Women And Birth" (38 adet) olduğu; en fazla mali destek veren kurumun "Avrupa Birliği" (12 adet) olduğu; en çok yayımlandığı konu alanının "Hemşirelik" (397 adet) olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Ağ haritası analizine göre en sık kullanılan anahtar kelimenin "tükenmişlik" olduğu; "iş tatmini", "stres" ve "Covid-19" anahtar kelimelerinin sıklıkla birlikte tercih edildiği; en çok atıf yapılan derginin "Journal of Advanced Nursing" olduğu; en çok atıf yapılan yazarın "Christina Maslach" olduğu; ortak yazarlık ülke analizinde Avustralya'nın ilk sırada olduğu ve ortak atıf analizinde Avustralya'daki "Griffith University" kurumunun ilk sırada olduğu bulgularına ulaşılmıştır. Çalışma sonucunda; konunun akademik zeminde ilgi çekiciliğini halen sürdürdüğü, konu ile ilgili çalışmalar için başta Avrupa Birliği olmak üzere çok sayıda kurum tarafından mali destek alınabileceği görülmüştür.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bibliyometrik Analiz, Ebe, Ebelik, Tükenmişlik, VoSviewer

1. INTRODUCTION

Burnout occurs as a result of chronic stress and is also characterised by symptoms of emotional and physical fatigue (1,2).

The concept of burnout was first introduced by Freudenberger to describe a situation characterised by fatigue, frustration and quitting the job among volunteer health workers, and then developed by Maslach and Jackson (3). Freudenberger defined burnout as "the state of exhaustion that occurs in the internal resources of the individual as a result of failure, wear and tear, decrease in energy and power or unsatisfied demands". Maslach, on the other hand, explained burnout with three sub-dimensions as "emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and decreased sense of personal accomplishment that employees may frequently encounter" (4,5). Emotional exhaustion is the most important determinant of burnout as the person feels overloaded and exhausted due to his/her work. Depersonalisation is the attitude and behaviour of the person towards the individuals he/she serves, devoid of emotion. Lack of personal accomplishment is defined as seeing oneself inadequate when faced with a problem and not being able to overcome the problems. If this dimension is high, the work motivation of the person decreases, the person experiences a lack of control and a feeling of helplessness (3).

The causes of burnout can be considered under two headings: personal and organisational. While personal causes are mostly explained by socio-demographic characteristics, organisational causes are explained by factors such as the nature of the work, the type of organisation, weekly working hours, role ambiguity, inability to participate in decisions and organisational climate (6). In our country, there are many research findings that socio-demographic characteristics are important determinants of burnout levels of healthcare workers (6–15). According to the literature findings, it is possible to say that basic socio-demographic variables such as occupation, age, education level, gender, marital status, income level, professional and institutional seniority play a determining role in the burnout level of healthcare workers.

The phenomenon of burnout also contains a feature that damages the health worker-patient relationship. Zengil et al. stated that as a result of burnout, the healthcare worker has a weaker use of judgement, responds late or inadequately to clinical changes, and a decrease in professional performance occurs, resulting in a loss of patient trust in the healthcare worker (16).

It is reported that midwives, who have a highly stressful job and establish an emotional bond with patients, are one of the professional groups prone to burnout. In the relationships of midwives experiencing burnout with patients, situations such as more limited communication and increased risk of applying wrong medical treatment can be seen (17,18). In addition, Fenwick et al. stated that burnout is common in midwives and that this situation negatively affects the health of midwives, and that burnout can shorten the career duration by reducing the quality of care provided by midwives. From this point of view, the phenomenon of burnout is not only important for the employee and the organisation, but it is also very important for the realisation of health care at the desired level (19).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Bibliometric analysis is the mathematical and statistical inference of academic publications in a discipline by using authors, keywords, countries where they are produced, institutions to which the authors are affiliated, citations, publication years and sources. In line with the findings obtained from bibliometric analysis, processes such as monitoring the development and trends of academic publications in the relevant discipline, making comparisons between countries and institutions, examining and evaluating journals over the years can be performed (20).

There are several bibliometric analysis tools in the literature. In this study, VOSviewer programme (version 1.6.19) was used because of its advantage in terms of mapping the findings. VOSviewer is a program that can create relationship networks through co-authorship, co-occurrence, co-occurrence, citation, bibliographic coupling or co-citation links by making use of elements in networks consisting of scientific publications, scientific journals, researchers, research institutions, countries, keywords and/or terms. These links also constitute the basic analyses of the programme. With these data, the programme can present three different visualisations of a map: network, layer and density (21).

"Web of Science" (WoS) database was used in this study. WoS is a database affiliated with Clarivate Analytics and has a respected position in academic communities all over the world in terms of both the number and quality of publications and citation status. WoS is important in Science Citation Index (SCI), Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) and Arts and Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI). In addition, not only articles but also documents such as books, theses, dissertations, papers and reports can be examined by bibliometric analysis method in WoS (22).

Although many bibliometric studies have been conducted in the literature, there is no study that reveals the current situation regarding "burnout" in midwives. For this reason, in this study, which was carried out to eliminate such a deficiency, firstly, the studies published in the journals in the WoS database were searched by selecting the keywords "Burnout" and "Midwifery" and "all fields" and a total of 852 studies were found. Then, only "research articles" were selected and research articles published between 2015-2024, which characterises the last 10 years as the time period, were searched. In line with the specified restrictions, 718 articles were accessed and analyses were performed on this number. Access to the data in the research was provided on 03/07/2024.

The main purpose of this study is to examine the bibliometric characteristics of the studies on the subject in the WoS database and to create a network map for these characteristics. The research questions formed in line with this purpose are given below:

1-How is the annual distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024 according to the number of publications?

2-How is the distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024 according to countries and institutions?

3-How is the distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024 according to authors and journals?

4-How is the distribution according to the organisations providing financial support for research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024?

5-How is the distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024 according to subject areas?

6-How is the keyword network and density map distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024?

7-How is the reference co-citation network analysis of publications, co-citation network analysis of journals and co-citation network analysis of authors of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024?

8-How is the country network in the co-authorship analysis and the university network in the co-citation analysis of the publications of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024?

Ethical review is not required as this study examines the literature published in databases.

3. RESULTS

The year-based distribution of research articles published in the period 2015-2024 on the subject of burnout in midwives in journals scanned in the Web of Science database is shown in Graph 1.

Graph 1. Year-based distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives

The number of articles published between 2015 and 2022 on the subject of burnout in midwives is in the 25-120 band, and it is seen that the publications mostly increase until 2023. In the journals scanned in the Web of Science database, the year in which the least number of articles on the subject was published was 2015 (25) and the year in which the most articles were published was 2022 (120). In 2023, there was a decrease in the number of articles published on the subject (110). In the first 6 months of 2024, 59 studies were published.

The country distribution of research articles published on burnout in midwives is shown in Graph 2.

Graph 2. Country-based distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives

The country with the highest number of research articles on burnout in midwives in journals scanned in the Web of Science database in the period 2015-2024 is Australia (219). Australia is followed by Iran (194) and England (110), respectively. Turkey ranks 16th with 15 studies.

The distribution of research articles published on burnout in midwives according to the institutions is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Institution-Based Distribution Of Research Articles on Burnout in Midwives

Institutions	Research Articles
Monash University	39
University of London	38
Griffith University	37
Tehran University of Medical Sciences	37
Curtin University	31
King S College London	24
Shahid Beheshti University Medical Sciences	23
Iran University of Medical Sciences	22
La Trobe University	22
Tabriz University of Medical Science	21

When we look at the distribution of research articles published on burnout in midwives according to the institutions, "Monash University" in Australia ranks first with 39 articles, followed by "University of London" in England with 38, "Griffith University" in Australia and "Tehran University of Medical Sciences" in Iran with 37 articles each.

The distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives published in WoS according to authors and the number of articles are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Author-Based Distribution of Research Articles on Burnout in Midwives

Authors	Research Articles
Van Bogaert, P.	15
Cross, W.	12
Fenwick, J.	12
Sidebotham, M.	12
Lam, L.	11
Franck, E.	10
Hegney, D.	10
Hildingsson, I.	10
Plummer, V.	10
Guo, Y.F.	9

When the distribution of the authors of the research articles published on the subject of burnout in midwives is evaluated, "Peter Van Bogaert" from the University of Antwerp in Belgium ranks first with 15 articles. "Wendy M. Cross" from Federation University in Australia, "Jennifer Fenwick" from University of Technology Sydney and "Mary Sidebotham" from Griffith University in the same country follow with 12 articles each.

The distribution of research articles published in WoS on burnout in midwives according to journals is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Journal-Based Distribution of Research Articles on Burnout in Midwives

Journals	Research Articles
Women and Birth	38
BMC Nursing	28
Journal of Advanced Nursing	28
Midwifery	28
Journal of Clinical Nursing	27
Journal of Nursing Management	26
Nursing Open	19
International Journal of Nursing Studies	17
Nursing and Midwifery Studies	16
BMC Health Services Research	14

In the research articles published on burnout in midwives, it is seen that the journal "Women And Birth" ranks first by far with 38 articles. It is followed by "BMC Nursing", "Journal of Advanced Nursing" and "Midwifery" with 28 articles each, "Journal of Clinical Nursing" with 27 articles and "Journal of Nursing Management" with 26 articles.

The distribution of organizations providing financial support for research articles published in WoS on burnout in midwives is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Distribution of Organizations Providing Financial Support for Research Articles on Burnout in Midwives

Organizations	Financial Supported Research Articles
European Union	12
Australian Government	8
US National Institutes of Health	8
UK National Institutes for Health Research	8
Tabriz University of Medical Sciences	8
Tehran University of Medical Sciences	8
United States Department of Health and Human Services	8
Mazandaran University of Medical Sciences	6
United Kingdom Burdett Nursing Foundation	4
Isfahan University of Medical Sciences	4

The most financial support to the research articles published on the subject of burnout in midwives was provided by the "European Union" with 12 times. The European Union was followed by the Australian Government, Institutes in the USA and the United Kingdom, and Universities in Iran with 8 financial support each.

The distribution of research articles published in WoS on burnout in midwives according to subject areas is shown in Table 5.

Figure 3. Reference Co-Citation Network Analysis of Publications

The most cited publication among the authors is Kristensen, T. S., Borritz, M., Villadsen, E., & Christensen, K. B. (2005)'s article titled "*The Copenhagen Burnout Inventory: A new tool for the assessment of burnout*" with 23 citations and 284 link strength. This article is followed by Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006)'s article titled "*Using thematic analysis in psychology*" with 21 citations and 37 link strength.

The shortness or length of the link distance between journals in the co-citation network represents the strength of the relationship between journals (26). In the journal co-citation network analysis, when the lowest number of citations a source receives is selected as 5, 398 of 4,393 sources meet the threshold value. As a result of the mapping, 7 clusters were obtained as red, green, blue, yellow, purple, turquoise and orange. Among these clusters, red cluster has 143 journals, green cluster has 88 journals, blue cluster has 50 journals, yellow cluster has 42 journals, purple cluster has 31 journals, turquoise cluster has 29 journals and orange cluster has 15 journals. The mapping related to the analysis is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Common Citation Network Analysis of Journals

The most cited journal among the journals is "Journal of Advanced Nursing" with 314 citations and 9.190 link strength. It is followed by "International Journal of Nursing Studies" with 296 citations and 7.933 link strength and "Journal of Nursing Management" with 293 citations and 8.568 link strength.

In the author co-citation analysis, when the lowest number of citations of an author was selected as 5, 219 of 8,292 authors met the threshold value. As a result of the mapping, a total of 8 clusters, 4,330 links and a total link strength of 12,698 were found. The mapping related to the analysis is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Authors' Common Citation Network Analysis

In the co-citation analysis, the most cited author is Christina Maslach with 55 citations and 712 link strength. The second most cited author is Linda H. Aiken with 48 citations and 536 link strength, and the third most cited author is Billie Hunter with 40 citations and 774 link strength.

In the co-authorship analysis, when the minimum number of documents cited from a country is selected as 5 in the mapping of the country network, 22 out of 64 countries meet the threshold value. As a result of the mapping, it was seen that there were 5 clusters, 110 links and 362 total link stems. The mapping related to the analysis is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Country Network in Co-authorship Analysis

In the co-authorship country analysis, Australia ranks first with 95 documents, 1,407 citations and 77 total linking power. Australia is followed by the UK (39 documents, 1,075 citations, 76 total link strength), the USA (24 documents, 723 citations, 67 total link strength) and Germany (10 documents, 456 citations, 56 total link strength).

The institutional network was analysed in order to determine which institutions were more interested in research articles on burnout in midwives. When the number of cited articles and the number of citations of the institutions were selected as the lowest 1, 493 out of 563 universities met the threshold value. As a result of the mapping, it was seen that a total of 20 clusters, 550 links and 725 total link strength were formed. The mapping related to the analysis is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. University Network in Joint Citation Analysis

Among the universities, "Griffith University" ranks first with 23 documents, 409 citations and 132 total link strength. This institution is followed by "Gold Coast University" with 4 documents,

241 citations and 94 total link strength and "La Trobe University" with 13 documents, 179 citations and 77 total link strength.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Due to the nature of the midwifery profession, midwives may experience burnout due to exposure to traumatic and difficult working conditions. It is stated that midwives experiencing burnout may provide inadequate care to their patients lacking empathy and therefore the professional image of midwifery, which is a professional profession, may be damaged by this situation (15). Considering both the protection of professional image and providing quality health services to patients, it is possible to say that academic studies that determine the causes of burnout in midwives, the effects of burnout and practices to eliminate burnout are important.

Bibliometric analyses on burnout in midwives are a valuable guide for those who want to start new studies in the field. Identifying research trends, gaps in the literature, the most effective studies, the most cited studies, leading institutions and key concepts is very important for researchers and practitioners to conduct more effective studies. This information contributes to developing an in-depth understanding of burnout in midwives and guiding future studies. In this direction, studies published in the journals in the Web of Science database on 3 July 2024 were searched by selecting the keywords "Burnout" and "Midwifery" and "all fields" and a total of 852 studies were found. Then, only "research articles" were selected and research articles published between 2015-2024, which characterises the last 10 years as the time period, were scanned. In line with the specified restrictions, 718 articles were accessed and analyses were performed on this number.

Looking at the annual distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024 according to the number of publications; It is seen that the number of articles published between 2015-2022 is in the 25-120 band and the publications mostly increased until 2023. In 2023, a decrease was observed in the studies published on the subject.

When the distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the relevant period according to countries and institutions is analysed; the country with the highest number of research articles is Australia. Australia was followed by Iran and the UK, respectively. When the distribution of published research articles according to institutions is analysed, "Monash University" in Australia ranks first, followed by "University of London" in England, "Griffith University" in Australia and "Tehran University of Medical Sciences" in Iran.

When the distribution of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024 is evaluated according to authors and journals, "Peter Van Bogaert" from the University of Antwerp in Belgium ranks first. He is followed by "Wendy M. Cross" from Federation University in Australia, "Jennifer Fenwick" from University of Technology Sydney in the same country and "Mary Sidebotham" from Griffith University. It is seen that the journal "Women And Birth" ranks first by far in the published research articles. It is followed by "BMC Nursing", "Journal of Advanced Nursing" and "Midwifery", "Journal of Clinical Nursing" and "Journal of Nursing Management.

When the distribution of the organisations that provided financial support to the research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS during the period examined is examined; the most financial support to the published research articles was provided by the "European Union". The European

Union was followed by the Australian Government, Institutes in the USA and the United Kingdom, and Universities in Iran.

In the period 2015-2024, the subject area in which the most research articles on burnout in midwives were published in WoS is "Nursing". This field is followed by "Public, Environmental and Occupational Health". The field of "Obstetrics & Gynaecology" ranks third.

When the network map of the research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS was analysed, it was found that the most frequently used keyword was "burnout", followed by "nursing" and "midwifery". In addition, it was found that the concept of "burnout" was frequently used together with the keywords "stress", "midwives" and "mental health" and also had strong relationships with the keywords "resilience" and "midwives". It was determined that the keywords "nursing", "midwifery", "job satisfaction", "stress" and "covid-19" were frequently preferred together in research articles. For this reason, it is thought that it will be useful to make associations with the subtopics mentioned in the studies to be conducted on burnout in midwives in the following years.

The most cited author among the authors of research articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the period 2015-2024 is Kristensen, T. S., Borritz, M., Villadsen, E., & Christensen, K. B. (2005) "The Copenhagen Burnout Inventory: A new tool for the assessment of burnout" with 23 citations and 284 link strength. This article is followed by Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006)'s article titled "Using thematic analysis in psychology" with 21 citations and 37 link strength. The most cited journal among the journals is "Journal of Advanced Nursing" with 314 citations and 9,190 link strength. It is followed by "International Journal of Nursing Studies" with 296 citations and 7.933 link strength and "Journal of Nursing Management" with 293 citations and 8.568 link strength. In the co-citation analysis, the most cited author is Christina Maslach with 55 citations and 712 link strength. The second most cited author is Linda H. Aiken with 48 citations and 536 link strength, and the third most cited author is Billie Hunter with 40 citations and 774 link strength.

In the co-authorship country analysis of the articles on burnout in midwives in WoS in the relevant period, Australia ranked first with 95 documents, 1,407 citations and 77 total link strength. Australia is followed by the UK (39 documents, 1,075 citations, 76 total link strength), USA (24 documents, 723 citations, 67 total link strength) and Germany (10 documents, 456 citations, 56 total link strength). Among the universities, "Griffith University" ranks first with 23 documents, 409 citations and 132 total link strength. This institution is followed by "Gold Coast University" with 4 documents, 241 citations and 94 total link strength and "La Trobe University" with 13 documents, 179 citations and 77 total link strength. It is noteworthy that Australian universities are in the top three in the University Network in the Co-Citation Analysis.

It is recommended that researchers who plan to conduct studies on burnout in midwives in the future should publish by considering the issues such as leading sources, co-authors, institutions providing financial support, topics and keywords that can be studied together, journals and publishing institutions.

Ethics Committee Approval: Ethics committee approval was not received in this study due to bibliometric analysis.

Informed Consent: Participant consent was not obtained due to the nature of the study being bibliometric.

Author Contributions: Concept - MÇ; Design - MÇ; Supervision - MÇ; Resources - MÇ; Materials - MÇ; Data Collection and/or Processing - MÇ; Analysis and/or Interpretation - MÇ; Literature Search - MÇ; Writing Manuscript - MÇ; Critical Review - MÇ; Other – MÇ

Declaration of Interests: The author has no conflicts of interest to declare.

Funding: The author declared that this study has received no financial support.

The study has not been presented anywhere before and has not been derived from a thesis.

REFERENCES

- Fenwick, J., Lubomski, A., Creedy, D.K., & Sidebotham, M.(2018). Personal, professional and workplace factors that contribute to burnout in Australian midwives. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 74(4), 852-863.
- Guo, Y.F., Luo Y.H., Lam, L., Cross. W., Plummer, V., & Zhang, J.P. (2018). Burnout and its association with resilience in nurses: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 27(1-2), 441-449.
- Kaçmaz, N. (2005). Tükenmişlik (Burnout) sendromu. *İstanbul Tıp Fakültesi Dergisi*, 68, 29-32.
- Bulut, H., Bozkurt, C., Kamiloğlu, D., Kızıloğlu, İ. (2024). Bir pandemi hastanesindeki sağlık çalışanlarının Covid-19 korkusunun tükenmişlik ile ilişkisinin incelenmesi. *Sağlık Akademisi Kastamonu*, 9(1), 46-60.
- Eriş, H., Havlioğlu, S., Küçüközkan, Y., & Özmen, S. (2017). Suriyeli mülteci kamplarının bulunduğu ilçelerde çalışan hemşire ve ebelerin tükenmişlik seviyesi: Şşanlıurfa örneği. *Uluslararası Sağlık Yönetimi ve Stratejileri Araştırma Dergisi*, 3(3), 326-339.
- Çankaya, M. (2017). Özel hastane çalışanlarının tükenmişlik düzeyleri ve bir alan uygulaması. *International Journal of Academic Value Studies (Javstudies JAVS)*, 3(9), 1-15.
- Taycan, O., Kutlu, L., Çimen, S., & Aydın, N. (2006). Relation between sociodemographic characteristics depression and burnout levels of nurse working in university hospital. *Anadolu Psikiyatri Dergisi*, 7(2), 100-108.
- Akbolat, M., & Işık, O. (2008). Sağlık çalışanlarının tükenmişlik düzeyleri: bir kamu hastanesi örneği. *Hacettepe Sağlık İdaresi Dergisi*, 11(2), 230-254.
- Ulusoy, H., Biçer, E. B., & Karabulut, N. (2012). Hastane yöneticilerinde tükenmişlik düzeyi. *Cumhuriyet Tıp Dergisi*, 34, 252-259.
- Helvacı, İ., & Turhan, M. (2013). Tükenmişlik düzeylerinin incelenmesi: Silifke’de görev yapan sağlık çalışanları üzerinde bir araştırma. *İşletme ve İktisat Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 1(4), 58-68.
- Uluköy, M. (2014). Sağlık çalışanlarının örgütsel adalet algısı ile tükenmişlik duyguları arasındaki ilişki: Bir uygulama. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 39, 213-225.
- Akyüz, İ. (2015). Hemşirelerin tükenmişlik ve depresyon düzeylerinin çalışma koşulları ve demografik özellikler açısından incelenmesi. *İşletme ve İktisat Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 3(1), 21-34.
- Toker, E., Turan, Z., & Seçkin, Z. (2020). Bir hastanede çalışan ebelerin mesleki örgütlenme durumu, iş doyum ve tükenmişlik düzeylerinin belirlenmesi. *Sağlık ve Toplum*, 1(4), 88-97.
- Acavut, G., & Korkmaz, S. (2022). Covid-19 pandemisinin doktor, hemşire ve ebelerin tükenmişlik durumlarına etkisinin belirlenmesi. *Turkish Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 16(1), 121-130.
- İnce, B., & Yılmaz, S. (2024). Ebelerin aidiyet, merhamet ve tükenmişlik düzeylerinin belirlenmesi. *Selçuk Sağlık Dergisi*, 5(2), 199-217.
- Zengil, S., Gürbüz, N., & Tör, İ. H. (2023). Pandemi sürecinde sağlık çalışanlarında sekonder travmatik stres, merhamet yorgunluğu ve tükenmişlik düzeylerinin değerlendirilmesi: Covid-19 pandemisi sırasındaki deneyim. *Akdeniz Tıp Dergisi*, 10(2), 295-301.
- Kaya, Ş. D., & Arıöz, A. (2014). Ebe ve hemşire öğrencilerinde tükenmişlik düzeyi ve etkileyen faktörler. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 31, 89-99.
- Eriş H., Barut, S., & Özkan, O. (2019). The effect of job stress on burnout in healthcare professionals. (Eds.), Albayrak, L., Açıkgöz, Ö., & Gökçen, E. In. *New horizons in health sciences*. 1st ed. Ankara: Gece Kitaplığı, p. 143-167.
- Jing, F. F., & Avery, G. C. (2016). Missing links in understanding the relationship between leadership and organizational performance. *The International Business & Economics Research Journal (Online)*, 15(3), 107-118.

20. Depren, Ö., Kartal, M. T., & Depren, S. K. (2018). Borsalarda oynaklık üzerine yayınlanmış akademik çalışmaların bibliyometrik analizi. *Bankacılık ve Sermaye Piyasası Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(6), 1-15.
21. Arslan, E. (2022). Sosyal bilim araştırmalarında VOSviewer ile bibliyometrik haritalama ve örnek bir uygulama. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 22(Özel Sayı 2), 33-56.
22. Akyüz, H. Ö., & Kalı, S. D. (2023). Hemşirelikte tamamlayıcı ve destekleyici tedaviler konulu yayınlara global bakış. *Sağlık Akademisyenleri Dergisi*, 10(1), 73-81.
23. Bulut, Z., & İli Demirel, N. (2022). Türkiye ve dünyadaki "hüzün turizmi" çalışmalarının bibliyometrik analizi. *Turizm ve İşletme Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(1), 67-88.
24. Demir, Y., Çiftçi, G. E., & Tüfekçi, İ. (2023). Kadına yönelik ekonomik istismara ilişkin bibliyometrik bir analiz. *Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli Üniversitesi SBE Dergisi* 13(1), 552-572.
25. Uçan, E. (2023). *Uluslararası ticaret ve finans anabilim dalında yapılan tezlerin bibliyometrik analizi*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt Üniversitesi, Ankara.
26. Doğan, T. G. B., Doğan, S., & Aykan, E. (2021). Liderlik tarzlarının bibliyometrik analizi. *Erciyes Akademi*, 35(1), 161-189.